

Membrane potential based assay for SLC5A7 using HEK-293 SLC5A7 OE cells

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Authors	Sara Tremolada ¹ , Loredana Redaelli ¹ , Lia Scarabottolo ¹
Affiliations	¹ Axxam S.p.A, Openzone Science Park, Bresso, Milan, Italy

Assay description

FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, upon activation of SLC5A7. The assay allows the detection of ion channel and transporter modulation by increasing or decreasing the fluorescent signal as cellular membrane potential changes. When cells are depolarized dye enters the cells, causing an increase in fluorescent signal, conversely, cells hyperpolarization results in dye exit and decreased fluorescence (Figure 1).

SLC5A7 is a hemicholinium-3 (HC-3)-sensitive transporter that mediates choline uptake by pre-synaptic terminal with a stoichiometry of 1 Na⁺: 1 choline. Therefore, being this transport electrogenic, it is eligible to be studied using the Membrane Potential dye.

Figure 1. Principal of a FLIPR[®] membrane potential dye assay. The assay measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, consequence of channels and transporters modulation. The fluorescent signal increases in intensity during membrane depolarization as dye follows the positively charged ions inside the cell. During membrane hyperpolarization, fluorescent signal decreases in intensity as dye follows the positively charged ions out of the cell.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC5A7 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 10'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂. At the same time of seeding cells were induced with 1 µg/mL Doxycycline (not induced control in parallel).

Membrane Potential assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated 30 minutes at RT in 20 µL/well of FMP-Blue-Dye (0.5X dye dissolved in Standard Tyrode's Buffer as indicated in the manufacturer manual) and plates analysed at FLIPR^{TETRA} reader using a λexc 510 - 545nm / λem 565 - 625 nm filter.

HC-3 inhibitor was tested at a concentration of 10 µM directly dissolved in the FMP-Blue-Dye solution and incubated therefore for 30 min at RT.

To test pharmacology 20 µL/well of Choline Chloride substrate (2X in Standard Tyrode's Buffer), starting from 3 mM, 1:3.162 dilution steps (8 concentrations, only buffer included) were online injected at the plate reader.

Data analysis

FLIPR^{TETRA} measurements obtained from different well replicates were analysed by using the Screenworks software (Molecular Devices, Version 3.0.1.4). Absolute Response (RFU) is obtained applying "Subtract Bias on Sample: n" (where n = Timepoint of compound injection) whereas Assay Window Response (ΔF/F₀) is obtained applying "Response over Baseline" correction (where Baseline = Timepoint -1 and -2 before activator injection) and "Background Subtraction". Data were then exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC). Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC₅₀/IC₅₀ values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 6).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC5A7
Synonyms	High Affinity Choline Transporter 1, CHT1
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 5 (Sodium/Choline Cotransporter)
UniProt ID	Q9GZV3
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE02H5-4 (HEK-SLC5A7-WTOE-p5-6)

Assay data

	Compound name (1)	Choline Chloride
	PubChem CID	6209
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, # 7017
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 17 μM
	Compound name (2)	HC-3
	PubChem CID	9399
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, # H108
	Mode of action	Inhibitor
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	IC ₅₀ = na Only one concentration of HC-3 was tested, showing an almost complete inhibition of the SLC. An inhibitor D/R is needed to calculate the IC50.

Discussion

A specific and dose-dependent response was obtained in the SLC5A7 cells induced with Doxycycline and treated with increasing doses of Choline Chloride substrate. Pre-incubation for 30 min with 10 μ M HC-3 almost completely abolished the fluorescence signal induced by treatment with Choline Chloride in the SLC5A7 cell line induced with Doxycycline, confirming the specificity of the detected signal.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).